

COST Action PROBE - Information exchange on UAS regulations & measurement principles

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1 Instrument overview and legal aspects

1.1 Introduction & historical overview

During the last couple of decades, uncrewed aircraft system (UAS) have emerged as a cost-effective, revolutionary technology with applications across a wide range of industries (Hassanalain and Abdelkefi, 2017): from healthcare (Roberts et al., 2023), research and rescue (Mayer et al., 2019; lob et al., 2020), agriculture (Rejeb et al., 2022) to parcel delivery (Pugliese et al., 2020), or even in sport (Russomanno et al., 2022). UAS are less expensive to operate compared to crewed aircraft and can be more flexible for deployment at hard to reach locations, where information is necessary but missing. This operational convenience, as well as the capability of repetitive and scalable mission planning, underscore the appeal and interest of the scientific community as well as industry, for their further development (FAA, 2022; Layman, 2022; Nex et al., 2022).

In this chapter the focus is posed only on UAS that are used for weather sensing purposes. Following the current community standards, these systems are often addressed as small research UAS, which encompasses all uncrewed aircraft with a maximum takeoff weight below 25 kg. This weight is a common limit for the UAS to be considered *small* both by European regulation and by the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA).

An essential advantage of UAS lies in their inherent ability to engage in new sampling strategies. Flight missions can provide measurements from diverse environments at multiple kinds of conditions (Sziroczak et al., 2022). At the same time, the cost to maintain and operate such a system is significantly lower than one of crewed aircraft (no human pilot is required, smaller / less demanding equipment, less environmental impact) and they pose as a great reusable option for repeated measurements and data collection, when needed (Pinto et al., 2021).

The initial deployment of primitive UAS for meteorological purposes can be traced back to the early 1970s when Konrad et al. (1970) explored their potential in gaining a better understanding of convective processes within the lower atmospheric boundary layer (ABL). However, the widespread use of UAS began to emerge over the last two decades, coinciding with the reduction in prices of electronic components, making it feasible for small research groups. Holland et al. (2001) and Curry et al. (2004) were instrumental in the development of the Aerosonde UAS and its inaugural deployment for meteorological measurements in the Arctic region. Few years later Martin et al. (2011) conducted the first vertical profile measurements of temperature and relative humidity up to 1500 m above ground level (agl) with a remarkable 10 cm resolution.

In the present scenario, with UAS technology firmly established and the expectation of further reductions in component costs, numerous researchers are exploring how a network of automated UAS could enhance weather forecast models. Bridging gaps in the measurement of thermodynamic and kinematic properties within the lower ABL is crucial for advancing weather forecasting models (Pinto et al., 2021). Research by Leuenberger et al. (2020) illustrates how drone observations can effectively fill spatial and temporal gaps in temperature and humidity data, particularly in countries with limited access to remote sensing technologies or in sparsely covered regions such as polar areas.

However, the continuous growth of usage of UAS has not been without challenges. Regulatory issues surrounding their operation and integration into existing airspace frameworks have become focal points of discussion. As it is possible to employ UAS in urban environments, ensuring safety while encouraging innovation has been a complex task for regulators and industry stakeholders (Nikodem et al., 2018; Denney et al., 2018). Moreover, miniaturised systems such as UAS also come with smaller power supplies, affecting their flight endurance, compared to longer flight times of bigger aircraft. Advancements in battery technology and propulsion systems are therefore essential (Pham et al., 2022), and already ongoing as UAS operation builds on momentum.

Lastly, environmental issues such as susceptibility to adverse weather conditions, including rain and icing,

present obstacles to reliable UAS operations (Muhammed and Virk, 2022). The combination of increasing interest to use UAS in science and industry, and these present issues that need to be addressed, creates a dynamic landscape in which evolution of UAS technology will in overall, advance multiple different fields of profession and push human knowledge further. As innovators navigate the intersection of regulatory, endurance, and environmental considerations, the future promises an even more integrated and significant role for UAS in our society. For further general information on UAS in meteorology, see Bange et al. (2021).

1.2 Basic measurement principles

1.2.1 Types of research UAS

From the aerodynamic perspective, there are two two significantly different principles of UAS flight:

1.2.1.1 Fixed-wing aircraft

A fixed-wing UAS, by definition, is a system capable of flight due to the lift generated by its wings when moving through the air (Mohsan et al., 2023; G. Fahlstrom and J. Gleason, 2012). In this context, these systems can be envisioned as scaled-down aircraft equipped solely with scientific sensors. It is essential for such systems to be in relative motion with respect to the surrounding air to achieve proper flight. Fixed-wing systems offer a distinct advantage in their ability to glide efficiently, offering greater endurance and lower power consumption than multi-rotor systems. This enables them to cover vast horizontal distances or execute vertical profiles to high altitudes. However, a fixed-wing system cannot sample at a stationary point as it needs to maintain a certain true airspeed (TAS) to generate lift.

The takeoff of these systems can be accomplished in various ways, including bungee launches, catapult launches, or even hand-tossing takeoffs. One crucial requirement for these systems is the availability of a relatively long, flat surface necessary for the landing procedure. While vertical take-off and landing (VTOL) systems address this issue, they are generally less efficient and offer only a fraction of the endurance of a standard fixed-wing model.

1.2.1.2 Multi-rotor UAS

On the other hand, multi-rotor UAS are systems that achieve flight by generating lift through rotating blades (Mohsan et al., 2023; G. Fahlstrom and J. Gleason, 2012). Although the principle for lift generation mirrors that of a helicopter, multi-rotor systems typically incorporate at least three rotors to ensure full manoeuvrability along all three directions of motion and rotation. These machines offer a significant advantage in their ability to take off and land vertically, even in tight spaces (for example during offshore operations from a boat), and maintain a fixed position in the air regardless of the surrounding air's motion.

However, unlike fixed-wing systems, multi-rotor UAS cannot glide. Consequently, their flight duration is generally shorter, requiring meticulous mission planning to ensure there is sufficient power available until the final moments of flight. The market for multi-rotor systems has experienced explosive growth in recent years, finding applications ranging from military purposes to extreme sports filming. Consequently, there is a wide variety of different frames and pre-built systems available. Nowadays, nearly all rotary-wing UAS utilise commercially available frames, and researchers can easily incorporate modular components to integrate custom atmospheric sensors.

1.3 Legal / regulatory limitations

Since the beginning of 2021, an EU-wide regulation for the operation of UAS is in force, based on a decision by the European Commission on 24 May 2019. The EU Drone Regulation applies in all EU Member States, as well as in associated states (Norway, Liechtenstein, Iceland, Switzerland), provided that Regulation (EU) 2019/947 has been ratified there.

If a UAS is to be operated, the following conditions apply regardless of any applicable authorisation requirement:

- Minimum age: A minimum age of 16 years (except for UAS certified in class C0).

- Registration requirement for all UAS pilots: Every pilot must register online at the national Federal Aviation Office and receives a registration number (e-ID).
- Compulsory insurance: Compulsory drone liability insurance is required by law for all drones.
- Respect for privacy: no recording of persons without permission (enshrined by national law not in the EU Drone Act)

Whether or not a flight permit is required for the intended use depends on three main factors: the size and weight of the UAS, the ownership of the area to be flown over, and the intended flight altitude. The larger and heavier the drone, the more likely it is that a flight permit will be required. The ownership of the area to be flown over must also be taken into account. In particular, a distinction needs to be made between private and non-private land (e.g. farmers using a drone over their own fields versus inspecting bridges or wind turbines in public areas). Population density is also an important factor. Proximity to industrial plants, highways, waterways or other infrastructure must also be taken into account. Depending on the intended use, higher flight altitudes may also be necessary. In general, similar to the weight and size factors, the higher the drone is to be flown, the more likely it is that a special flight permit will be required and a more extensive approval process.

The drones operation is divided into the following three categories (application scenarios): Open, Specific and Certified Category.

1.3.1 Open Category

The least restrictive category is the open category. If the assessment of the factors of size and weight, the ownership of the terrain to be flown over and the planned flight altitude results in a low risk, the open category is awarded. A distinction is made between 3 or 5 sub-categories from A1 to A3. These can be divided into urban areas and outside urban areas. Further the sub-categories determines which 'CE class' of drone can be flown. Depending on the sub-category, the EU Certificate of Competence (A1/A3), or the EU Remote Pilot Certificate (A2) is required. In addition, national regulations of the national air traffic regulations must be respected. The following must always be taken into account:

- A maximum flight altitude of 120 m
- Flights should only be carried out within the pilot's visual range and should not take place over gatherings of people unless the drone has the appropriate CE certification
- The UAS should weigh less than 25 kg
- No objects may be dropped and no dangerous objects may be transported
- If the drone is equipped with a camera, care must be taken to ensure that people are not photographed or filmed without their consent and that the material is not published.

1.3.2 Specific Category

In the special category, the approval process is slightly more extensive than in the open category and the pilot must hold a A2 certificate. In order to obtain a permit to fly, the risk posed by the proposed flight(s) must be assessed. Either the risk is assessed and evaluated using a Predefined Risk Assessment (PDRA) or a Specific Operations Risk Assessment (SORA). The PDRA is the quicker route, but requires that the flight mission corresponds to a standard scenario defined by EASA or the national authorities. These European Standard Scenarios (STS), which describe a predefined procedure, are available since January 2024. Operators will no longer require to obtain an operating licence if the planned flight project is an STS. There are currently two published STS (STS-01 or STS-02). Accordingly, it is possible to submit a declaration to the competent aviation authority for these two scenarios (so-called declarations stating whether STS-01 or STS-02 is to be performed).

If the planned mission is not a standard scenario, a risk analysis in the form of a SORA (Specific Operations Risk Assessment) must be carried out for the planned flight project and submitted to the competent national aviation authority. The preparation of a SORA describes a methodology for classifying the risk of the planned UAV flight and identifying mitigation measures and safety objectives. The assessment comprises

a ten-step process that begins with the description of the mission and the risk assessment on the ground and in the air.

The ground risk describes the risk that can arise for people, property or critical infrastructure if they are hit by a drone. The most important parameters are:

- the population density at the flight location
- the flight altitude, i.e. whether the drone is still within the pilot's visual line of sight (VLOS) or beyond visual line of sight (BVLOS)
- the size and take-off weight of the drone,
- as well as possible mitigation measures (e.g. use of a parachute or additional ground crew).

The air risk takes into account the probability of encountering crewed aircraft in the airspace. This results from:

- The density of crewed air traffic in the airspace
- The planned mitigation measures.

The combination of the two factors is used to define a risk assessment for the planned flight operation, which is described with a categorisation in SAIL (Specific Assurance Integrity Level). The higher the categorisation in SAIL (I - IV), the higher the risk of the planned flight. This category is therefore aimed at (semi-)professional operators who, for example, carry out agricultural flights, survey flights, inspection flights and flights over crowds of people or in urban areas - including in BVLOS operations. BVLOS operation.

The above information is merely a summary of the currently applicable regulations without any guarantee that they are correct or up to date. For more details and possible changes/adjustments to the applicable regulations, please refer to the information provided by the European Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) <https://www.easa.europa.eu/en/light/topics/drones>.

1.4 Overview of quantities that can be derived

1.4.1 Meteorological sampling: general aspects and scalars

The most essential element when it comes to probing the atmosphere is the ability to correctly measure meteorological parameters directly related to the state of the weather, such as temperature T , relative humidity (RH) and air density ρ . So far, UAS have been widely used for monitoring weather events affecting road traffic, such as rain, fog or storms (Sziroczak et al., 2022). Thermal infrared sensors mounted on UAS have also been used for measuring surface temperatures, with comparison with meteorological data on the ground (Wu et al., 2022). Regarding atmospheric measurements, fixed-wing small aircraft have been used for data collection in the lower troposphere, including parameters such as wind speed, wind direction and heat fluxes, e.g. by Martin et al. (2011). A literature review of previously used and existing UAS can be found in Elston et al. (2015). As miniaturised T and RH sensors become more and more common, and easily adjustable on UAS, attention has been focused on the various aspects that need to be taken into account when performing measurements with these systems (Jacob et al., 2018). Similar development has been ongoing for multi-rotor systems too (Broisy et al., 2017), with its own set of considerations (Greene et al., 2018). For further general information on sensors aboard small research UAS in meteorology, see Bange et al. (2021).

1.4.2 Wind measurement techniques using fixed-wing UAS

As explained in Rautenberg et al. (2018) there are different types of wind measurements approach when using a fixed wing UAS.

1.4.2.1 No-flow sensor algorithm

Mayer et al. (2012) introduced the No Flow Sensor Algorithm (NFSA) to estimate mean horizontal wind without requiring additional sensors on the UAS, utilising only data from the inertia navigation system (INS).

However, this method necessitates flying missions in circular patterns, either plain circles or helix patterns for vertical profiles. Rautenberg et al. (2018) demonstrated that racetrack patterns could also be used, provided the wind estimation averaging window covers more than two full closed loops. However, the algorithm relies on certain assumptions: constant TAS of the aircraft and constant wind speed within the averaging window. The primary limitations of this approach are the high uncertainty in wind direction retrieval and the time resolution.

1.4.2.2 Pitot-tube algorithm

Another approach supplements INS data with information from a Pitot tube, often referred to as the Pitot Tube Algorithm (PTA). In this method, a Pitot tube sensor is mounted on the UAS, providing TAS information. Unlike the NFSA, the PTA does not require specific flight paths, although changing the flying direction can simplify the underlying equations. However, this algorithm assumes that the TAS components perpendicular to the aircraft are negligible. Consequently, the equations for this algorithm are not directly solvable, necessitating a temporal average to resolve the mathematical problem. Furthermore, the PTA faces challenges in retrieving the vertical wind component due to significantly high uncertainty in this direction, compared to common absolute values. Additionally, if the UAS is programmed to climb or descend, the PTA tends to underestimate the horizontal wind component because the assumption of no vertical components is violated. Despite these challenges, Rautenberg et al. (2018) demonstrates that the PTA offers superior accuracy and higher temporal resolution compared to the NFSA.

1.4.2.3 Multi-hole probe algorithm

A more complex method for wind speed retrieval involves utilising a multi-hole probe (MHPA) mounted on the UAS. This approach, detailed in Bange (2009), does not disregard the perpendicular TAS components, as they can be measured by the multiple holes of the sensor. Consequently, the equations of the model can be solved, allowing for the calculation of all three components of the wind vector at every time step. This method provides a sampling frequency suitable for turbulence analysis. However, a drawback of this approach is the extensive calibration required for the 5-hole probe (5HP) itself. Calibration necessitates a wind tunnel, and calibration polynomials must be derived for different pitch and sideslip angles concerning the probe, as indicated by (Rautenberg et al., 2019a). This calibration process is highly time-consuming, involving the investigation of at least 442 different points within the functioning range of the sensor (+20, -20 degrees in each direction). Moreover, these polynomials are influenced by the Reynolds number, adding complexity to the calibration process. One would need to calibrate the 5HP across the entire TAS range the UAS might encounter. Fortunately, many fixed-wing UAS operate by maintaining a constant TAS (or attempting to do so). Therefore, few additional calibrations in the proximity of the prescribed TAS would be adequate to ensure accurate sampling of the wind speed at any time during flight.

1.4.3 Wind measurement techniques using multi-rotor UAS

1.4.3.1 Tilt angle method

The tilt angle method, pioneered by Neumann and Bartholmai (2015), involves hovering the multicopter at a specific point and observing how much it tilts toward the incoming wind to maintain position. This method offers the advantage of not requiring additional sensors for the UAS, making it particularly valuable for multi-rotor UAS with limited endurance. Recent studies have demonstrated that even very small multi-rotor UAS can resolve the vertical wind component if adequately calibrated (Wildmann and Wetz, 2022). Current research is focused on exploring various instruments and strategies for determining the calibration function. Additionally, scientists are investigating the influence of multi-rotor shape, number of rotors, and mass on the precision of the wind estimation algorithm. This method provides a reasonably accurate estimate of the wind, especially when the UAS's primary task extends beyond wind estimation itself (Brosy et al., 2017; Chang et al., 2020).

The sampling frequency of this method depends significantly on the size of the copter, as it relies on aerodynamic forces and the copter's response to wind variations. However, finding the optimal balance

between a larger multi-rotor (more sensitive to airflow) and a lighter system (lower inertia) remains a topic of ongoing investigation (Hattenberger et al., 2023).

1.4.3.2 Sonic anemometer equipped UAS

Another method for wind speed retrieval involves equipping the flying system with a sonic anemometer, as discussed in studies by Palomaki et al. (2017), Shimura et al. (2018), and Donnell et al. (2018). Unlike other methods, the sonic anemometer doesn't require specific sensor calibration (as most of the times it is provided by the manufacturer of the sensor itself), but it presents its own set of challenges.

Choosing an appropriate placement for the sonic anemometer is crucial to avoid degradation of wind measurements due to induced flow from the rotors. One commonly used configuration places the sonic anemometer on a structure above the copter, several rotor diameters away from the rotors themselves (Thielicke et al., 2021). Recent studies suggest an improved positioning on a horizontal structure pointing towards the front of the flying system, with the UAS required to turn into the wind direction (Ghirardelli et al., 2023). Fortunately, many commercially available autopilot systems already incorporate functions to achieve this.

Sonic anemometers can offer high sampling frequencies in the hundreds of Hertz range. However, post-processing algorithms must account for the copter's motion as well as potential interference with rotor rotational frequencies and the Eigen frequencies of the mounting structure. Additionally, sonic anemometers can be quite heavy, weighing several kilograms. This added weight significantly reduces the overall UAS endurance and increases the risk in case of a failure event.

1.4.3.3 Multi-hole sensors and hot wires

Another approach studied for wind retrieval onboard multi-rotor UAS involves using multi-hole probes, Pitot tubes, or pressure sensors, as discussed by Prudden et al. (2018). Similar to sonic anemometers, the challenge lies in determining the correct sensor placement. However, this technique only allows measurement of wind speed, not wind direction, which necessitates a separate measurement method like the tilt angle method. While a 5-hole probe (5HP) would make the sensor insensitive to changes in the system's attitude, devices like pressure sensors or Pitot tubes must always be oriented facing the incoming wind. Achieving this condition without a proper servo mechanism becomes challenging for different wind speed ranges.

Recently, a working group from the University of Stuttgart, as mentioned in Molter and Cheng (2020), designed a UAS equipped with a hot wire anemometer for wind measurements. Despite offering excellent wind data in terms of frequencies, using hot wires on a UAS presents multiple challenges. Hot wires are inherently fragile devices, demanding careful consideration during takeoff and landing procedures. Moreover, it might be impossible to design a system in the usual landing configuration due to the delicate nature of fine wires. Additionally, a hot wire requires an extensive calibration procedure, which is sensitive to ambient temperature. This sensitivity demands extra caution when using such a device on a UAS intended to fly in all seasons throughout the year.

1.4.4 Aerosol particle measurements

Usage of UAS for air pollution monitoring has grown more and more appealing, as there is a necessity for data collection above the altitudes typically covered by ground based stations and at more complex sites with multiple obstacles, i.e. areas unreachable by crewed aircraft (Villa et al., 2016). A variety of UAS types (fixed-wing, multi-rotor) with various kinds of dimensions have been employed in urban centres so far, covering different spatial and temporal levels (Lambey and Prasad, 2021).

In recent years, there has been development of new low-cost sensors and novel UAS platforms, for monitoring air pollutants such as particulate matter (PM) (Kezoudi et al., 2022; Girdwood et al., 2020). These UAS have also been used for real time monitoring of numerous other pollutants such as NO₂ (Gu et al., 2018), black carbon and CO₂ (Chang et al., 2016; Corrigan et al., 2008), CO and ozone (Alvear et al., 2015), as well as SO₂ (Simo et al., 2021). These systems also provide measurements with multiple sensors that

cover several of the aforementioned pollutants, as well as meteorological parameters.

Other studies include more specific research topics and reveal the diversity and variety of operations that can be undertaken with UAS. Specifically, a multi-rotor system was used for measuring dust particles (which contribute to PM₁₀) originating from mining activities (Alvarado et al., 2017; Alvarado et al., 2015). A case study related to pollution caused by traffic, was done by measuring pollutants near at a river bridge with an octo-copter (Weber et al., 2017). Bio-aerosol sensors on small quad-copters were employed for measuring ice nucleation particles at heights close to the surface at different terrain types (Bieber et al., 2020). Ice nucleation particles have also been studied with fixed-winged aircraft up to altitudes of 2.5 km (Schrod et al., 2017). Other possibilities that have been explored with UAS were measurements of Saharan dust plumes (Mamali et al., 2018), ultra-fine particles in the atmospheric boundary layer (Altstädter et al., 2015), heating rate, albedo and solar absorption (Ramana et al., 2007), gases from active volcanoes (Stix et al., 2018), and biomass burning emissions (Vernooij et al., 2022).

1.4.5 Other applications

UAS have been extensively used for mapping of land and sea surfaces, as they can effectively cover large horizontal distances in a short time period and often with relatively low effort. Various studies have used UAS in this manner, for successfully mapping tree species diversity (Liu et al., 2021), marine litter (Gonçalves et al., 2020), non-submerged aquatic vegetation (Husson et al., 2016), forest structure (Kuželka and Surový, 2018), coastal topography and bathymetry (Brodie et al., 2019), wetland restoration (Harvey et al., 2019), surface breakages from earthquakes (Lin et al., 2019), as well as for monitoring cultural heritage at coastal areas (Papakonstantinou et al., 2019). Especially in agriculture applications, UAS are employed frequently to monitor plant growth, track wildlife or even to disperse pesticides or fertilisers.

1.5 Tabular overview of instrument types

For further information on UAS sensors, including resolution, range, available products, uncertainties/limitations, please see Bange et al. (2021).

A non-complete overview on current types of UAS, manufacturers, sensors and corresponding literature is given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Fixed Wing UAS currently in use

Name	Developer	MTOW	Payload	Endurance	Measured Variables
SUMO (Reuder et al., 2009)	Bergen University	580 g	140 g	~30 min	T (SHT75, 2 Hz), RH (SHT75, 2 Hz), P(MS 5611, 2 Hz), surf T (MLX90614, 2 Hz), 3-D flow vector (100 Hz)
DataHawk2 (Hamilton et al., 2022)	University of Colorado Boulder	1.7 kg	—	~1 h	T (RSS-421, cold wire 800 Hz), RH (RSS-421, 5 Hz), P (RSS-421, 5 Hz), 3-D flow vector (800 Hz)
RAAVEN (Boer et al., 2022)	University of Colorado Boulder	1.8 kg	—	~2.5 h	T (RSS-421, fine wire, 400 Hz), RH (RSS-421, 250 Hz), P (RSS-421, 250 Hz), 3-D flow vector (50 Hz)
BST S1 (Boer et al., 2021)	University of Colorado Boulder Black Swift Technology	2.5 kg	—	~1.5 h	T (EE-03, 4 Hz), RH (EE-03, 4 Hz), 3-D flow vector (100 Hz)
Talon-3 (Talon, 2021)	University of Colorado Boulder	3 kg	—	~45 min	T (RSS904, 2 Hz), RH (RSS904, 2 Hz), P(RSS904, 2 Hz) 3-D flow vector (10 Hz)
BLUECAT5 (Witte et al., 2017)	University of Kentucky	5 kg	0.5 Hz	~45 min	T (iMet-XQ, 1 Hz), RH (iMet-XQ, 1 Hz), 3-D flow vector (100 Hz)
M ² AV (Kroonenberg et al., 2008)	Braunschweig University	6 kg g	1.5 kg	~45 min	T (HMP50, 1 Hz), RH (HMP50, 1 Hz), 3-D flow vector (100 Hz)
TTwistor (Boer et al., 2021)	University of Colorado Boulder	6.4 kg	2 kg	~3 h	T (RSS904, 2 Hz), RH (RSS904, 2 Hz), P(RSS904, 2 Hz), 3-D flow vector (100 Hz)
CoBi (Kezoudi et al., 2021)	The Cyprus Institute	7 kg	2 kg	~1 h	T(HC2-ROPCB), RH(HC2-ROPCB), CO ₂ (HPP), aerosol (Alphasense N2, UCASS)
MASC-3 (Rautenberg et al., 2019b)	Uni Tübingen	8 kg	1 kg	~1.5 h	T(fine-wire, SHT31, 100 Hz), RH (SHT31, 1 Hz), dew point (CMH, 5 Hz), 3-D flow vector (100 Hz)
ALADINA (Altstädter et al., 2015)	Braunschweig University	25 kg	2.8 kg	~40 min	T (fine-wire, 100 Hz), RH (P14 Rapid, 3 Hz), aerosol 3-D flow vector (100 Hz)
BOREAL (Alaoui-Sosse et al., 2022)	Université de Toulouse	25 Kg	5 kg	~9 h	T (SHT75, 100 Hz), RH (SHT75, 100 Hz), P(HCE0611, 100 Hz) 3-D flow vector (100 Hz)

Table 2: Multi-rotor UAS currently in use

Name	Developer	MTOW	Payload	Endurance	Measured Variables
SWUF-3D fleet (Wetz et al., 2021)	DLR	650 g	—	~12 min	T (HYT271, 100 Hz), RH (HYT271, 100 Hz), 3-D wind vector (attitude)
Coptersonde (Segales et al., 2020)	University of Oklahoma	2.4 kg	205 g	~18.5 min	T (iMet-XF therm, 20 Hz), RH (HYT-271, 20 Hz), P (MS5611, 20 Hz), 2-D wind vector (attitude)
ANDroMeDa (Molter and Cheng, 2020)	University of Stuttgart	5 kg	—	~19 min	3-D wind vector (hot wire)
MeteoDrone (Meteomatics, 2022)	Meteomatics AG	5 kg	1 kg	~22 min	T (1 Hz), RH (0.25 Hz), P (4 Hz), dew point, 2-D wind vector (attitude)
Munin (Galle et al., 2021)	Chalmers University of Technology	6 kg	2 kg	~30 min	T (BME280, 1 Hz), RH (BME280, 1 Hz), P (BME280, 1 Hz), CO ₂ (FlowEVO F3, 1 Hz), H ₂ S (Alphasense H2S-A, 1 Hz), SO ₂ (Alphasense SO2-A, 1 Hz), 2-D wind vector (sonic)
MetSprite wxUAS (Menapia, 2023)	Menapia Ltd	—	1 kg	~40 min	T, RH, P, 3-D wind vector (sonic)
MASC-MC (Bramati et al., 2024)	Uni Tübingen	8 kg	1 kg	~25 min	T (SHT31, 1 Hz), RH (SHT31, 1 Hz), P (BME280, 1 Hz), CO ₂ (SCD30, 1 Hz), PM2.5 – 5 – 10 (Alphasense N2, 1 Hz), 2-D wind vector (attitude)
MUST (Chang et al., 2020)	Academia Sinica	8.4 kg	1.6 kg	~30 min	T (SHT31, 1 Hz), RH(SHT31, 1 Hz), P(BME280, 1 Hz), PM2.5(AM520, 1 Hz), BC(AE51, 1 Hz), air sampling, O3 (POM, 1 Hz), 2-D wind vector (attitude)
WASPP (Asher et al., 2021)	NOAA	15 kg	6 kg	~20 min	T (HMP110, 1 Hz), RH (HMP110, 1 Hz), P (EPRB-2, 1 Hz), air sampling, 2-D wind vector (sonic)
ALICE (Lampert et al., 2020)	TU Braunschweig	25 kg	8 kg	~15 min	T(HMP110, TSYS01, 100 Hz), RH (HMP110, Rapid P14, 100 Hz), P (5812-0150-B, 100 Hz), air sampling

2 Recommendations for network operation

2.1 UAS as complementary to remote sensing

As a powerful tool for in-situ data acquisition, UAS can be used as a complementary tool for remote sensing validation studies, from which the application of both approaches can be improved. UAS data have been studied for identifying the boundary layer height (BLH), estimated from micro-pulse LiDAR (Wang et al., 2021). Laser scanning from a UAS has also been used for a comparison with a scanning LiDAR for estimation of tree trunk and branches volume and density, essential parameters for tree modelling (Brede et al., 2019). A swarm of small UAS measuring horizontal wind, has been shown to have comparable resolution to capturing incoming flow as LiDAR at a rural field site (Wetz et al., 2021). Sensors on the ground such as radiometers, have been compared with thermal cameras from UAS regarding thermal measurements (Torres-Rua et al., 2018), while LiDAR and UAS have been utilised for tracking small-scale morphological changes in a drainage basin (Borrelli et al., 2019). This shows that in numerous different fields of science, scientific questions arise that could be tackled using different methods, therefore promoting interdisciplinary collaboration and sharing of knowledge by experts on different topics. Advancement of UAS can therefore prove quite useful for in-situ data necessary for validation of remote sensing instruments, used in a variety of subjects.

2.2 WMO UAS Demonstration Campaign

The WMO Uncrewed Aircraft Systems Demonstration Campaign (UAS-DC) is a collaborative project to evaluate the potential of weather-sensing UAS in operational upper-air observing networks. Scheduled from March to September 2024, UAS-DC will demonstrate the readiness of UAS to contribute to the WIGOS Regional/Global Basic Observing Network (RBON/GBON) .

The Unmanned Aircraft Systems Demonstration Campaign (UAS-DC) focuses on several key objectives according to the WMO UAS DC ¹:

The campaign aims to demonstrate the current capabilities of various UAS models and evaluate their potential to address operational needs for upper-air observations and observational gaps within the WIGOS Global Basic Observing Network (GBON) and/or Regional Basic Observing Network (RBON). Additionally, it seeks to showcase the ability of UAS and their data processing systems to deliver data in an interoperable format suitable for use by relevant applications and forecasting systems. Another goal is to assess and report on the impacts of UAS observations on important WMO application areas and forecasting systems. Moreover, the campaign aims to identify areas requiring development to enable UAS to efficiently, economically, and environmentally contribute operationally to WIGOS. Lastly, it will identify and propose recommendations concerning regulatory conditions affecting UAS that may influence their capability to contribute effectively to WIGOS.

The collected data of the WMO UAS DC can be accessed via the UAS-DC Data Repository. It is designed for receiving, storing, formatting, and making available the data generated by participants in the WMO UAS Demonstration Campaign.

2.3 VITAL HErZ

The Tübingen work group will perform UAS flights during the VITAL² campaign in August 2024, with a focus on validating and improving 3D wind and turbulence estimations from multi-copters against common references. Data will be uploaded operationally to the WMO UAS DC server for downstream applications such as UAS data assimilation experiments.

¹<https://community.wmo.int/en/uas-demonstration>

²<https://www.herz.uni-bonn.de/wordpress/index.php/vital-campaigns/>

2.4 VALUAS DWD

During the VALUAS (Validation of remote sensing and numerical simulations of the DWD using UAS) campaigns a total of more than 140 flights with the platform MASC-3 have been performed with the goal of using the UAS to validate several LiDAR systems. Preliminary parts of the results can be found in Boverter et al., [2024](#)

2.5 Instrument set-up, maintenance, calibration, measurement configuration

The most important aspects of instrument set-up, maintenance, calibration, measurement configuration are described in the preceding subsections in Section 2 and – for more details – in the literature cited there. For a summary including examples for flight strategies we refer to Bange et al. ([2021](#)).

2.6 QA/QC (quality assurance & control)

After proper preparation of the UAS flight campaign including calibration and suited flight strategies, and conducting the experiments, a large data set is gathered. First steps of QA/QC include diagrams in time and space of the collected atmospheric data, e.g. temperature, water vapour, wind vectors along flight tracks and vertical profiles. A comprehensive Fourier spectral analysis of all flight sections and measured quantities reveals systematic measurement errors like electromagnetic hum and temporal resolution.

After this basic search and quantification of systematic measurement errors, the obtained data sets (in time and space) can of course be compared and validated against other measurement systems. The challenge with UAS turbulence measurements, e.g., is that only few other systems are able to provide a comparable resolution in time and space, and a sufficient accuracy. Actually only other micro-meteorological instruments come into consideration, i.e. eddy covariance (EC) stations and research towers equipped with high-resolution instruments like sonic anemometers for instance. However, these instruments do not cover large volumes but mainly are representative for their measurement location only (spot measurements) in contrast to research UAS that cover large distances of tens of kilometres horizontally and several thousand metres vertically.

In the end, the most robust QA/QC is the comparison with theory, especially boundary-layer meteorology for data measured in the lower troposphere, and of course turbulence theory for atmospheric flow. Most suited statistical tools are EC, auto-correlation functions, and structure functions, in order to calculate turbulent fluxes, integral length scales, and check for local-isotropic inertia sub-range of turbulence. From there the significance of the turbulence data can be quantify, both with respect to the systematic and random statistical uncertainty. For more information on research aircraft in general, UAS, and turbulence QA/QA, please see Bange et al. ([2021](#)) and Desjardins et al. ([2021](#)).

3 Data formats and file standards

3.1 Data formats

The BUFR (Binary Universal Form for the Representation of meteorological data) format is a global standard for meteorological data established by the WMO (World Meteorological Organization, [2019](#)) to replace alphanumeric formats. It is used in operational settings such as data transport and data assimilation. netCDF (Network Common Data Format) is another common and efficient self-describing data format (Rew and Davis, [1990](#)). Both formats are used during the WMO UAS demo campaign.

3.2 File standards

For the WMO UAS demo campaign, a netCDF file standard was established to facilitate automatic conversion to BUFR. Apart from this, there are no other established file standards for UAS data exchange that the authors are aware of.

4 Processing algorithms and retrieval codes

For post-processing of meteorological time series, including UAS data, the PARMESAN Python package has been developed by Büchau et al. (2023). It facilitates a variety of calculations and conversions for temperature, humidity, gas concentration, wind and turbulence quantities as well as time series analysis primitives such as spectral analysis, variograms, diurnal cycles, and more.

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